

Affy ID	Gene Symbol	Gene name	P	FC
A) up-regulated genes in 6 h time point				
203936_s_at	MMP9	matrix metalloproteinase 9 (gelatinase B, 92kDa gelatinase, 92kDa type IV collagenase)	0.000	3.68
203889_at	SCG5	secretogranin V (7B2 protein)	0.000	3.46
1554997_a_at	PTGS2	prostaglandin-endoperoxide synthase 2	0.000	3.11
204748_at	PTGS2	prostaglandin-endoperoxide synthase 2	0.000	2.80
214079_at	DHRS2	dehydrogenase/reductase (SDR family) member 2	0.000	2.70
208394_x_at	ESM1	endothelial cell-specific molecule 1	0.000	2.64
202672_s_at	ATF3	activating transcription factor 3	0.000	2.64
223878_at	INPP4B	inositol polyphosphate-4-phosphatase, type II, 105kDa	0.000	2.32
205680_at	MMP10	matrix metalloproteinase 10 (stromelysin 2)	0.001	2.24
213680_at	KRT6C	keratin 6C	0.000	2.21
207850_at	CXCL3	chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 3	0.000	2.20
211719_x_at	FN1	fibronectin 1	0.000	1.96
228964_at	PRDM1	PR domain containing 1, with ZNF domain	0.000	1.94
233223_at	NEDD9	neural precursor cell expressed, developmentally down-regulated 9	0.000	1.91
215223_s_at	SOD2	superoxide dismutase 2, mitochondrial	0.000	1.88
235236_at	DOCK2	dedicator of cytokinesis 2	0.000	1.87
210495_x_at	FN1	fibronectin 1	0.000	1.80
213998_s_at	DDX17	DEAD (Asp-Glu-Ala-Asp) box polypeptide 17	0.001	1.77
201170_s_at	BHLHB2	basic helix-loop-helix domain containing, class B, 2	0.001	1.77
236678_at	JAG1	jagged 1 (Alagille syndrome)	0.000	1.75
212464_s_at	FN1	fibronectin 1	0.000	1.75
202357_s_at	CFB	complement factor B	0.002	1.74
216442_x_at	FN1	fibronectin 1	0.000	1.74
208719_s_at	DDX17	DEAD (Asp-Glu-Ala-Asp) box polypeptide 17	0.001	1.72
234700_s_at	RNASE7	ribonuclease, RNase A family, 7	0.001	1.68
238831_at	TMEM33	transmembrane protein 33	0.001	1.67
227740_at	UHMK1	U2AF homology motif (UHM) kinase 1	0.001	1.67
211708_s_at	SCD	stearoyl-CoA desaturase (delta-9-desaturase)	0.003	1.65
228250_at	FNIP1	folliculin interacting protein 1	0.001	1.64
203038_at	PTPRK	protein tyrosine phosphatase, receptor type, K	0.001	1.62
235852_at	STON2	stonin 2	0.001	1.62
224797_at	ARRDC3	arrestin domain containing 3	0.001	1.61
244396_at	G3BP1	GTPase activating protein (SH3 domain) binding protein 1	0.001	1.60
206172_at	IL13RA2	interleukin 13 receptor, alpha 2	0.001	1.59
222787_s_at	TMEM106B	transmembrane protein 106B	0.002	1.58
202284_s_at	CDKN1A	cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 1A (p21, Cip1)	0.001	1.55
215008_at	TLL2	tolloid-like 2	0.002	1.55
235003_at	UHMK1	U2AF homology motif (UHM) kinase 1	0.001	1.54
210511_s_at	INHBA	inhibin, beta A	0.002	1.54
211162_x_at	SCD	stearoyl-CoA desaturase (delta-9-desaturase)	0.005	1.54
214290_s_at	HIST2H2AA4	histone cluster 2, H2aa4	0.002	1.54
205032_at	ITGA2	integrin, alpha 2 (CD49B, alpha 2 subunit of VLA-2 receptor)	0.001	1.53
218280_x_at	HIST2H2AA3	histone cluster 2, H2aa3	0.002	1.53
234699_at	RNASE7	ribonuclease, RNase A family, 7	0.002	1.53
204151_x_at	AKR1C1	aldo-keto reductase family 1, member C1	0.009	1.52
231723_at	SNX12	sorting nexin 12	0.002	1.51
229115_at	DYNC1H1	dynein, cytoplasmic 1, heavy chain 1	0.003	1.50
223278_at	GJB2	gap junction protein, beta 2, 26kDa	0.001	1.50
233488_at	RNASE7	ribonuclease, RNase A family, 7	0.003	1.48
211653_x_at	AKR1C2	aldo-keto reductase family 1, member C2	0.010	1.48
209699_x_at	AKR1C2	aldo-keto reductase family 1, member C2	0.013	1.45
227223_at	RBM39	RNA binding motif protein 39	0.005	1.44
222450_at	TMEPAI	transmembrane, prostate androgen induced RNA	0.003	1.44
209189_at	FOS	v-fos FBJ murine osteosarcoma viral oncogene homolog	0.003	1.44
205220_at	GPR109B	G protein-coupled receptor 109B	0.004	1.43
229545_at	C20orf42	chromosome 20 open reading frame 42	0.004	1.41
208814_at	HSPA4	heat shock 70kDa protein 4	0.004	1.40
210229_s_at	CSF2	colony stimulating factor 2 (granulocyte-macrophage)	0.005	1.40
1557227_s_at	TPR	translocated promoter region (to activated MET oncogene)	0.005	1.40
208151_x_at	DDX17	DEAD (Asp-Glu-Ala-Asp) box polypeptide 17	0.005	1.39
1560679_at	LOC151438	hypothetical protein LOC151438	0.004	1.39
1552656_s_at	UHMK1	U2AF homology motif (UHM) kinase 1	0.004	1.39
201578_at	PODXL	podocalyxin-like	0.004	1.39
223333_s_at	ANGPTL4	angiopoietin-like 4	0.004	1.39
211000_s_at	IL6ST	interleukin 6 signal transducer (gp130, oncostatin M receptor)	0.005	1.38
226084_at	MAP1B	microtubule-associated protein 1B	0.005	1.38
204463_s_at	EDNRA	endothelin receptor type A	0.005	1.38
216594_x_at	AKR1C1	aldo-keto reductase family 1, member C1	0.017	1.36
204358_s_at	FLRT2	fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2	0.005	1.35
205966_at	TAF13	TAF13 RNA polymerase II, TATA box binding protein (TBP)-associated factor, 18kDa	0.006	1.34
1562234_a_at	NAV3	neuron navigator 3	0.005	1.34

208003_s_at	NFAT5	nuclear factor of activated T-cells 5, tonicity-responsive	0.010	1.32
204475_at	MMP1	matrix metalloproteinase 1 (interstitial collagenase)	0.011	1.32
1553055_a_at	SLFN5	schlafen family member 5	0.006	1.32
227149_at	NEDD9	neural precursor cell expressed, developmentally down-regulated 9	0.010	1.32
216015_s_at	NLRP3	NLR family, pyrin domain containing 3	0.006	1.31
203502_at	BPGM	2,3-bisphosphoglycerate mutase	0.007	1.31
205476_at	CCL20	chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 20	0.008	1.31
227314_at	ITGA2	integrin, alpha 2 (CD49B, alpha 2 subunit of VLA-2 receptor)	0.006	1.31
208083_s_at	ITGB6	integrin, beta 6	0.006	1.31
223217_s_at	NFKBIZ	nuclear factor of kappa light polypeptide gene enhancer in B-cells inhibitor, zeta	0.009	1.30
201730_s_at	TPR	translocated promoter region (to activated MET oncogene)	0.008	1.30
209774_x_at	CXCL2	chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 2	0.008	1.29
201041_s_at	DUSP1	dual specificity phosphatase 1	0.007	1.28
201996_s_at	SPEN	spen homolog, transcriptional regulator (Drosophila)	0.015	1.28
208960_s_at	KLF6	Kruppel-like factor 6	0.007	1.27
206463_s_at	DHRS2	dehydrogenase/reductase (SDR family) member 2	0.010	1.27
238430_x_at	SLFN5	schlafen family member 5	0.008	1.26
227399_at	VGLL3	vestigial like 3 (Drosophila)	0.010	1.26
1553962_s_at	RHOB	ras homolog gene family, member B	0.008	1.26
214055_x_at	BAT2D1	BAT2 domain containing 1	0.018	1.26
205064_at	SPRR1B	small proline-rich protein 1B (cornifin)	0.026	1.25
211814_s_at	CCNE2	cyclin E2	0.015	1.25
203821_at	HBEGF	heparin-binding EGF-like growth factor	0.010	1.23
214447_at	ETS1	v-ets erythroblastosis virus E26 oncogene homolog 1 (avian)	0.012	1.23
38037_at	HBEGF	heparin-binding EGF-like growth factor	0.010	1.22
202600_s_at	NRIP1	nuclear receptor interacting protein 1	0.013	1.21
207351_s_at	SH2D2A	SH2 domain protein 2A	0.011	1.21
219736_at	TRIM36	tripartite motif-containing 36	0.014	1.21
236620_at	RIF1	RAP1 interacting factor homolog (yeast)	0.020	1.21
214701_s_at	FN1	fibronectin 1	0.012	1.20
235281_x_at	AHNAK	AHNAK nucleoprotein	0.012	1.20
1555832_s_at	KLF6	Kruppel-like factor 6	0.011	1.20
222449_at	TMEPAI	transmembrane, prostate androgen induced RNA	0.013	1.19
1555229_a_at	C1S	complement component 1, s subcomponent	0.018	1.18
211948_x_at	BAT2D1	BAT2 domain containing 1	0.020	1.18
243999_at	SLFN5	schlafen family member 5	0.014	1.18
215779_s_at	HIST1H2BG	histone cluster 1, H2bg	0.014	1.18
227337_at	ANKRD37	ankyrin repeat domain 37	0.015	1.18
227530_at	AKAP12	A kinase (PRKA) anchor protein (gravin) 12	0.016	1.18
203691_at	PI3	peptidase inhibitor 3, skin-derived (SKALP)	0.025	1.18
223453_s_at	DKFZP564J0863	DKFZP564J0863 protein	0.014	1.18
241397_at	EHF	ets homologous factor	0.022	1.18
232035_at	HIST1H4H	histone cluster 1, H4h	0.018	1.16
237746_at	SFRS11	splicing factor, arginine/serine-rich 11	0.019	1.16
242583_at	STON2	stonin 2	0.017	1.16
235409_at	MGA	MAX gene associated	0.019	1.16
203395_s_at	HES1	hairly and enhancer of split 1, (Drosophila)	0.022	1.16
236524_at	TM2D1	TM2 domain containing 1	0.023	1.16
1565868_at	CD44	CD44 molecule (Indian blood group)	0.019	1.15
203021_at	SLPI	secretory leukocyte peptidase inhibitor	0.029	1.15
211559_s_at	CCNG2	cyclin G2	0.017	1.15
1554980_a_at	ATF3	activating transcription factor 3	0.017	1.15
209911_x_at	HIST1H2BD	histone cluster 1, H2bd	0.019	1.14
227529_s_at	AKAP12	A kinase (PRKA) anchor protein (gravin) 12	0.022	1.14
206569_at	IL24	interleukin 24	0.018	1.13
203158_s_at	GLS	glutaminase	0.020	1.13
203628_at	IGF1R	insulin-like growth factor 1 receptor	0.019	1.12
205196_s_at	AP1S1	adaptor-related protein complex 1, sigma 1 subunit	0.019	1.12
211506_s_at	IL8	interleukin 8	0.022	1.12
210387_at	HIST1H2BG	histone cluster 1, H2bg	0.028	1.12
205807_s_at	TUFT1	tuftelin 1	0.020	1.11
202124_s_at	TRAK2	trafficking protein, kinesin binding 2	0.023	1.11
241762_at	FBXO32	F-box protein 32	0.027	1.11
218723_s_at	C13orf15	chromosome 13 open reading frame 15	0.022	1.11
204612_at	PKIA	protein kinase (cAMP-dependent, catalytic) inhibitor alpha	0.021	1.10
205195_at	AP1S1	adaptor-related protein complex 1, sigma 1 subunit	0.021	1.10
213668_s_at	SOX4	SRY (sex determining region Y)-box 4	0.023	1.09
202843_at	DNAJB9	DnaJ (Hsp40) homolog, subfamily B, member 9	0.023	1.09
205681_at	BCL2A1	BCL2-related protein A1	0.023	1.08
209173_at	AGR2	anterior gradient homolog 2 (Xenopus laevis)	0.031	1.08
209183_s_at	C10orf10	chromosome 10 open reading frame 10	0.027	1.07
211372_s_at	IL1R2	interleukin 1 receptor, type II	0.023	1.07
202628_s_at	SERPINE1	serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade E (nexin, plasminogen activator inhibitor type 1), memb	0.024	1.07
229706_at	TCERG1	transcription elongation regulator 1	0.032	1.07

204864_s_at	IL6ST	interleukin 6 signal transducer (gp130, oncostatin M receptor)	0.027	1.06
210517_s_at	AKAP12	A kinase (PRKA) anchor protein (gravin) 12	0.034	1.06
242352_at	NIPBL	Nipped-B homolog (Drosophila)	0.035	1.06
221563_at	DUSP10	dual specificity phosphatase 10	0.027	1.06
209765_at	ADAM19	ADAM metallopeptidase domain 19 (meltrin beta)	0.027	1.06
215843_s_at	TLL2	tolloid-like 2	0.029	1.06
208727_s_at	CDC42	cell division cycle 42 (GTP binding protein, 25kDa)	0.027	1.05
1559883_s_at	SAMHD1	SAM domain and HD domain 1	0.027	1.05
204614_at	SERPINB2	serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade B (ovalbumin), member 2	0.029	1.05
208180_s_at	HIST1H4H	histone cluster 1, H4h	0.031	1.05
239596_at	SLC30A7	solute carrier family 30 (zinc transporter), member 7	0.029	1.04
223940_x_at	MALAT1	metastasis associated lung adenocarcinoma transcript 1 (non-coding RNA)	0.031	1.04
213428_s_at	COL6A1	collagen, type VI, alpha 1	0.033	1.04
212226_s_at	PPAP2B	phosphatidic acid phosphatase type 2B	0.035	1.04
242784_at	ETS2	v-ets erythroblastosis virus E26 oncogene homolog 2 (avian)	0.031	1.04
219927_at	FCF1	FCF1 small subunit (SSU) processome component homolog (S. cerevisiae)	0.038	1.03
242944_at	FAM83A	family with sequence similarity 83, member A	0.032	1.03
210172_at	SF1	splicing factor 1	0.037	1.03
232033_at	USP37	ubiquitin specific peptidase 37	0.039	1.03
208961_s_at	KLF6	Kruppel-like factor 6	0.031	1.02
235287_at	CDK6	cyclin-dependent kinase 6	0.035	1.02
224726_at	MIB1	mindbomb homolog 1 (Drosophila)	0.036	1.02
222585_x_at	KRCC1	lysine-rich coiled-coil 1	0.036	1.02
244447_at	KLF10	Kruppel-like factor 10	0.037	1.02
202917_s_at	S100A8	S100 calcium binding protein A8	0.047	1.02
209398_at	HIST1H1C	histone cluster 1, H1c	0.035	1.01
1559970_at	LOC730034	hypothetical protein LOC730034	0.033	1.01
201169_s_at	BHLHB2	basic helix-loop-helix domain containing, class B, 2	0.042	1.01
205990_s_at	WNT5A	wingless-type MMTV integration site family, member 5A	0.035	1.01
235277_at	AMOTL1	angiomin like 1	0.038	1.01
242916_at	CEP110	centrosomal protein 110kDa	0.039	1.01
214455_at	HIST1H2BC	histone cluster 1, H2bc	0.039	1.01
230000_at	RNF213	ring finger protein 213	0.039	1.01
222150_s_at	tcag7.1314	hypothetical protein LOC54103	0.035	1.00
204863_s_at	IL6ST	interleukin 6 signal transducer (gp130, oncostatin M receptor)	0.038	1.00
227454_at	TAOK1	TAO kinase 1	0.040	1.00
220085_at	HELLS	helicase, lymphoid-specific	0.037	1.00
243963_at	SDCCAG8	serologically defined colon cancer antigen 8	0.037	1.00
202627_s_at	SERPINE1	serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade E (nexin, plasminogen activator inhibitor type 1), memb	0.035	0.99
208084_at	ITGB6	integrin, beta 6	0.035	0.99
1557078_at	SLFN5	schlafen family member 5	0.035	0.99
229070_at	C6orf105	chromosome 6 open reading frame 105	0.036	0.99
219878_s_at	KLF13	Kruppel-like factor 13	0.038	0.99
211074_at	FOLR1	folate receptor 1 (adult)	0.040	0.99
231618_s_at	SUNC1	Sad1 and UNC84 domain containing 1	0.037	0.99
202150_s_at	NEDD9	neural precursor cell expressed, developmentally down-regulated 9	0.042	0.99
215338_s_at	NKTR	natural killer-tumor recognition sequence	0.043	0.99
212067_s_at	C1R	complement component 1, r subcomponent	0.045	0.99
209949_at	NCF2	neutrophil cytosolic factor 2 (65kDa, chronic granulomatous disease, autosomal 2)	0.042	0.99
231248_at	CST6	cystatin E/M	0.043	0.99
202842_s_at	DNAJB9	DnaJ (Hsp40) homolog, subfamily B, member 9	0.037	0.98
223997_at	FNIP1	folliculin interacting protein 1	0.040	0.98
237999_at	ZDHHC13	zinc finger, DHHC-type containing 13	0.042	0.98
224250_s_at	SECISBP2	SECIS binding protein 2	0.039	0.98
209750_at	NR1D2	nuclear receptor subfamily 1, group D, member 2	0.043	0.98
244677_at	PER1	period homolog 1 (Drosophila)	0.045	0.98
214657_s_at	TncRNA	trophoblast-derived noncoding RNA	0.040	0.98
238563_at	ABI1	abl-interactor 1	0.043	0.98
226535_at	ITGB6	integrin, beta 6	0.039	0.97
227478_at	SETBP1	SET binding protein 1	0.040	0.97
1558015_s_at	ACTR2	ARP2 actin-related protein 2 homolog (yeast)	0.042	0.97
214456_x_at	SAA2	serum amyloid A2	0.044	0.97
221830_at	RAP2A	RAP2A, member of RAS oncogene family	0.042	0.97
205003_at	DOCK4	dedicator of cytokinesis 4	0.043	0.97
204803_s_at	RRAD	Ras-related associated with diabetes	0.045	0.97
238755_at	LOC644943	similar to peptidylglycine alpha-amidating monooxygenase COOH-terminal interactor	0.039	0.96
216493_s_at	IGF2BP3	insulin-like growth factor 2 mRNA binding protein 3	0.042	0.96
1552543_a_at	STON2	stonin 2	0.040	0.96
207517_at	LAMC2	laminin, gamma 2	0.040	0.96
220658_s_at	ARNTL2	aryl hydrocarbon receptor nuclear translocator-like 2	0.041	0.96
209928_s_at	MSC	musculin (activated B-cell factor-1)	0.042	0.96
223138_s_at	DHX36	DEAH (Asp-Glu-Ala-His) box polypeptide 36	0.045	0.96
235341_at	LOC144871	hypothetical protein LOC144871	0.043	0.96
228438_at	TRPA1	transient receptor potential cation channel, subfamily A, member 1	0.043	0.95

229553_at	PGM2L1	phosphoglucomutase 2-like 1	0.043	0.95
211085_s_at	STK4	serine/threonine kinase 4	0.045	0.95
203890_s_at	DAPK3	death-associated protein kinase 3	0.042	0.95
216031_x_at	HN1L	hematological and neurological expressed 1-like	0.043	0.95
216056_at	CD44	CD44 molecule (Indian blood group)	0.044	0.95
212468_at	SPAG9	sperm associated antigen 9	0.045	0.94
222858_s_at	DAPP1	dual adaptor of phosphotyrosine and 3-phosphoinositides	0.047	0.94
234994_at	KIAA1913	KIAA1913	0.049	0.94
204464_s_at	EDNRA	endothelin receptor type A	0.050	0.94
1558080_s_at	LOC144871	hypothetical protein LOC144871	0.047	0.94
224771_at	NAV1	neuron navigator 1	0.050	0.94
212062_at	ATP9A	ATPase, Class II, type 9A	0.045	0.93
238460_at	FAM83A	family with sequence similarity 83, member A	0.049	0.93
219010_at	C1orf106	chromosome 1 open reading frame 106	0.045	0.93
201107_s_at	THBS1	thrombospondin 1	0.046	0.93
206877_at	MXD1	MAX dimerization protein 1	0.047	0.93
210818_s_at	BACH1	BTB and CNC homology 1, basic leucine zipper transcription factor 1	0.048	0.93
211668_s_at	PLAU	plasminogen activator, urokinase	0.045	0.92
216841_s_at	SOD2	superoxide dismutase 2, mitochondrial	0.049	0.92
207198_s_at	LIMS1	LIM and senescent cell antigen-like domains 1	0.048	0.92

B) down-regulated genes in 6 h time point

1557285_at	LOC727738	similar to Amphiregulin precursor (AR) (Colorectum cell-derived growth factor) (CRDGF)	0.000	-2.11
222316_at	VDP	vesicle docking protein p115	0.000	-1.80
212193_s_at	LARP1	La ribonucleoprotein domain family, member 1	0.001	-1.61
242424_at	LETMD1	LETM1 domain containing 1	0.001	-1.56
228729_at	CCNB1	cyclin B1	0.002	-1.54
218755_at	KIF20A	kinesin family member 20A	0.004	-1.53
240452_at	GSPT1	G1 to S phase transition 1	0.002	-1.53
215729_s_at	VGLL1	vestigial like 1 (Drosophila)	0.001	-1.51
202240_at	PLK1	polo-like kinase 1 (Drosophila)	0.005	-1.48
230779_at	TNRC6B	trinucleotide repeat containing 6B	0.002	-1.46
240231_at	AZIN1	antizyme inhibitor 1	0.003	-1.44
214918_at	HNRPM	heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein M	0.003	-1.43
227420_at	TNFAIP8L1	tumor necrosis factor, alpha-induced protein 8-like 1	0.006	-1.41
219235_s_at	PHACTR4	phosphatase and actin regulator 4	0.005	-1.40
201185_at	HTRA1	HtrA serine peptidase 1	0.007	-1.39
201896_s_at	PSRC1	proline/serine-rich coiled-coil 1	0.006	-1.37
201853_s_at	CDC25B	cell division cycle 25 homolog B (S. pombe)	0.006	-1.36
229518_at	FAM46B	family with sequence similarity 46, member B	0.005	-1.35
228252_at	PIF1	PIF1 5-to-3 DNA helicase homolog (S. cerevisiae)	0.010	-1.30
1559139_at	NOC2L	nucleolar complex associated 2 homolog (S. cerevisiae)	0.006	-1.30
238988_at	TOP1	topoisomerase (DNA) I	0.006	-1.30
232278_s_at	DEPDC1	DEP domain containing 1	0.011	-1.29
217678_at	SLC7A11	solute carrier family 7, (cationic amino acid transporter, y+ system) member 11	0.010	-1.29
204379_s_at	FGFR3	fibroblast growth factor receptor 3 (achondroplasia, thanatophoric dwarfism)	0.007	-1.28
1555673_at	KRTAP2-1	keratin associated protein 2-1	0.022	-1.28
235419_at	ERRF1	ERBB receptor feedback inhibitor 1	0.007	-1.27
207711_at	C20orf117	chromosome 20 open reading frame 117	0.010	-1.27
221899_at	PFAAP5	phosphonoformate immuno-associated protein 5	0.008	-1.27
210966_x_at	LARP1	La ribonucleoprotein domain family, member 1	0.010	-1.24
235190_at	CALM2	calmodulin 2 (phosphorylase kinase, delta)	0.010	-1.23
220779_at	PADI3	peptidyl arginine deiminase, type III	0.014	-1.22
229764_at	FAM79B	family with sequence similarity 79, member B	0.017	-1.21
242121_at	RNF12	ring finger protein 12	0.013	-1.20
235803_at	CRLF3	cytokine receptor-like factor 3	0.013	-1.20
1557293_at	LOC440993	hypothetical gene supported by AK128346	0.014	-1.20
244503_at	BDNFOS	brain-derived neurotrophic factor opposite strand	0.012	-1.20
1566901_at	TGIF1	TGFB-induced factor homeobox 1	0.021	-1.20
225124_at	PPP1R9B	protein phosphatase 1, regulatory (inhibitor) subunit 9B	0.016	-1.20
244803_at	YY1AP1	YY1 associated protein 1	0.014	-1.20
229692_at	API5	apoptosis inhibitor 5	0.012	-1.20
231735_s_at	PRO1073	PRO1073 protein	0.013	-1.19
214710_s_at	CCNB1	cyclin B1	0.018	-1.19
225777_at	C9orf140	chromosome 9 open reading frame 140	0.016	-1.18
242751_at	PRDX6	peroxiredoxin 6	0.014	-1.17
239922_at	CCDC142	coiled-coil domain containing 142	0.018	-1.16
206023_at	NMU	neuromedin U	0.018	-1.16
239228_at	CSNK2A1	casein kinase 2, alpha 1 polypeptide	0.016	-1.15
224562_at	WASF2	WAS protein family, member 2	0.019	-1.15
237246_at	SMC4	structural maintenance of chromosomes 4	0.020	-1.14
209916_at	DHTKD1	dehydrogenase E1 and transketolase domain containing 1	0.020	-1.13
207165_at	HMMR	hyaluronan-mediated motility receptor (RHAMM)	0.023	-1.13
230733_at	MRCL3	myosin regulatory light chain MRCL3	0.018	-1.13

204318_s_at	GTSE1	G-2 and S-phase expressed 1	0.024	-1.13
209758_s_at	MFAP5	microfibrillar associated protein 5	0.023	-1.12
222958_s_at	DEPDC1	DEP domain containing 1	0.025	-1.12
227663_at	LOC728555	hypothetical protein LOC728555	0.019	-1.12
204255_s_at	VDR	vitamin D (1,25- dihydroxyvitamin D3) receptor	0.020	-1.12
238756_at	MTPN	myotrophin	0.027	-1.11
224013_s_at	SOX7	SRY (sex determining region Y)-box 7	0.027	-1.11
226517_at	BCAT1	branched chain aminotransferase 1, cytosolic	0.020	-1.10
1558220_at	MUC20	mucin 20, cell surface associated	0.022	-1.10
240513_at	EIF3M	eukaryotic translation initiation factor 3, subunit M	0.021	-1.10
1557014_a_at	C9orf122	chromosome 9 open reading frame 122	0.020	-1.10
223080_at	GLS	glutaminase	0.023	-1.09
215190_at	EIF3M	eukaryotic translation initiation factor 3, subunit M	0.023	-1.09
1569519_at	KIAA1245	KIAA1245	0.023	-1.08
220318_at	EPN3	epsin 3	0.024	-1.08
214782_at	CTTN	cortactin	0.024	-1.08
225473_at	C20orf117	chromosome 20 open reading frame 117	0.029	-1.08
214964_at	KIAA1856	KIAA1856 protein	0.023	-1.08
204641_at	NEK2	NIMA (never in mitosis gene a)-related kinase 2	0.025	-1.08
202580_x_at	FOXM1	forkhead box M1	0.026	-1.08
213075_at	OLFML2A	olfactomedin-like 2A	0.027	-1.07
228762_at	LFNG	LFNG O-fucosylpeptide 3-beta-N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase	0.025	-1.07
223315_at	NTN4	netrin 4	0.027	-1.07
201843_s_at	EFEMP1	EGF-containing fibulin-like extracellular matrix protein 1	0.023	-1.07
204083_s_at	TPM2	tropomyosin 2 (beta)	0.027	-1.06
203706_s_at	FZD7	frizzled homolog 7 (Drosophila)	0.029	-1.06
223895_s_at	EPN3	epsin 3	0.026	-1.06
1556053_at	DNAJC7	DnaJ (Hsp40) homolog, subfamily C, member 7	0.025	-1.06
209290_s_at	NFIB	nuclear factor I/B	0.027	-1.06
1555947_at	FAM120A	family with sequence similarity 120A	0.031	-1.05
222310_at	SFRS15	splicing factor, arginine/serine-rich 15	0.027	-1.05
206487_at	UNC84A	unc-84 homolog A (C. elegans)	0.040	-1.04
204654_s_at	TFAP2A	transcription factor AP-2 alpha (activating enhancer binding protein 2 alpha)	0.038	-1.04
209709_s_at	HMMR	hyaluronan-mediated motility receptor (RHAMM)	0.036	-1.04
208502_s_at	PITX1	paired-like homeodomain 1	0.034	-1.04
212013_at	PXDN	peroxidasin homolog (Drosophila)	0.029	-1.04
232716_at	EDG2	endothelial differentiation, lysophosphatidic acid G-protein-coupled receptor, 2	0.029	-1.04
218425_at	TRIAD3	TRIAD3 protein	0.034	-1.04
203764_at	DLG7	discs, large homolog 7 (Drosophila)	0.035	-1.03
1553970_s_at	CEL	carboxyl ester lipase (bile salt-stimulated lipase)	0.042	-1.03
223577_x_at	MALAT1	metastasis associated lung adenocarcinoma transcript 1 (non-coding RNA)	0.029	-1.03
218494_s_at	SLC2A4RG	SLC2A4 regulator	0.033	-1.03
204092_s_at	AURKA	aurora kinase A	0.037	-1.03
208079_s_at	AURKA	aurora kinase A	0.037	-1.02
1562062_at	KIAA1245	KIAA1245	0.032	-1.02
1558088_a_at	UBE2I	ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2I (UBC9 homolog, yeast)	0.036	-1.02
201369_s_at	ZFP36L2	zinc finger protein 36, C3H type-like 2	0.042	-1.02
209714_s_at	CDKN3	cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 3 (CDK2-associated dual specificity phosphatase)	0.043	-1.02
202454_s_at	ERBB3	v-erb-b2 erythroblastic leukemia viral oncogene homolog 3 (avian)	0.033	-1.02
238444_at	ZNF618	zinc finger protein 618	0.034	-1.02
213605_s_at	LOC728411	similar to Beta-glucuronidase precursor	0.035	-1.02
210220_at	FZD2	frizzled homolog 2 (Drosophila)	0.035	-1.02
1559490_at	LRCH3	leucine-rich repeats and calponin homology (CH) domain containing 3	0.034	-1.01
235392_at	IRS1	insulin receptor substrate 1	0.035	-1.01
226663_at	ANKRD10	ankyrin repeat domain 10	0.039	-1.01
204317_at	GTSE1	G-2 and S-phase expressed 1	0.040	-1.01
229674_at	SERTAD4	SERTA domain containing 4	0.032	-1.01
236978_at	MED13	mediator complex subunit 13	0.033	-1.01
209909_s_at	TGFB2	transforming growth factor, beta 2	0.038	-1.01
224516_s_at	CXXC5	CXXC finger 5	0.036	-1.00
1555758_a_at	CDKN3	cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 3 (CDK2-associated dual specificity phosphatase)	0.044	-1.00
236641_at	KIF14	kinesin family member 14	0.038	-1.00
201842_s_at	EFEMP1	EGF-containing fibulin-like extracellular matrix protein 1	0.035	-1.00
228590_at	PTCD3	Pentatricopeptide repeat domain 3	0.036	-1.00
227801_at	TRIM59	tripartite motif-containing 59	0.039	-1.00
1556339_a_at	UBE1C	ubiquitin-activating enzyme E1C (UBA3 homolog, yeast)	0.038	-0.99
1565651_at	ARF1	ADP-ribosylation factor 1	0.044	-0.99
215114_at	SEN3P3	SUMO1/sentrin/SMT3 specific peptidase 3	0.038	-0.99
210649_s_at	ARID1A	AT rich interactive domain 1A (SWI-like)	0.048	-0.99
231846_at	FOXRED2	FAD-dependent oxidoreductase domain containing 2	0.039	-0.98
205192_at	MAP3K14	mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 14	0.037	-0.98
242688_at	TRIP12	thyroid hormone receptor interactor 12	0.038	-0.98
202705_at	CCNB2	cyclin B2	0.042	-0.98
228512_at	PTCD3	Pentatricopeptide repeat domain 3	0.044	-0.98

266_s_at	CD24	CD24 molecule	0.037	-0.98
238714_at	RAB12	RAB12, member RAS oncogene family	0.042	-0.97
202870_s_at	CDC20	cell division cycle 20 homolog (S. cerevisiae)	0.043	-0.97
224321_at	TMEFF2	transmembrane protein with EGF-like and two follistatin-like domains 2	0.038	-0.97
239331_at	FLJ43663	hypothetical protein FLJ43663	0.039	-0.97
219165_at	PDLIM2	PDZ and LIM domain 2 (mystique)	0.040	-0.97
1556338_at	UBE1C	ubiquitin-activating enzyme E1C (UBA3 homolog, yeast)	0.042	-0.97
225332_at	KRTAP4-7	keratin associated protein 4-7	0.042	-0.96
228235_at	MGC16121	hypothetical protein MGC16121	0.040	-0.96
202575_at	CRABP2	cellular retinoic acid binding protein 2	0.041	-0.96
244766_at	LOC440354	PI-3-kinase-related kinase SMG-1 pseudogene	0.042	-0.96
201312_s_at	SH3BGRL	SH3 domain binding glutamic acid-rich protein like	0.043	-0.96
240482_at	HDAC3	histone deacetylase 3	0.043	-0.95
1570143_at	ZNF251	zinc finger protein 251	0.044	-0.95
210230_at	LOC728965	hypothetical protein LOC728965	0.044	-0.95
229422_at	NRD1	nardilysin (N-arginine dibasic convertase)	0.044	-0.95
232174_at	EXT1	exostoses (multiple) 1	0.045	-0.95
224215_s_at	DLL1	delta-like 1 (Drosophila)	0.043	-0.95
1556820_a_at	DLEU2	deleted in lymphocytic leukemia, 2	0.044	-0.94
201904_s_at	CTDSPL	CTD small phosphatase-like	0.045	-0.94
209172_s_at	CENPF	centromere protein F, 350/400ka (mitosin)	0.048	-0.94
242265_at	BRD8	bromodomain containing 8	0.044	-0.94
232442_at	BCAR1	breast cancer anti-estrogen resistance 1	0.045	-0.94
232521_at	PCSK7	proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 7	0.045	-0.93
215390_at	C9orf5	chromosome 9 open reading frame 5	0.046	-0.93
228121_at	TGFB2	transforming growth factor, beta 2	0.048	-0.93
239091_at	CCDC52	coiled-coil domain containing 52	0.046	-0.93
203407_at	PPL	periplakin	0.045	-0.93